

PREVALENCE OF SMART PHONE ADDICTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE NURSING STUDENTS AT COLLEGE OF NURSING NAWABSHAH

Roja Muskan^{*1}, Sana Niaz Ahmed², Abdul Karim Bhiyoon³

^{*1,2}GBSN, College of Nursing Female Nawabshah, Affiliated Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women, Shaheed Benazirabad

³Senior Nursing Lecturer, College of Nursing Female Mirpur Khas, Affiliated Peoples University of Medical & Health Sciences for Women, Shaheed Benazirabad.

^{*1}rojamuskan27@gmail.com, ²sanatanvisana@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18753807>

Keywords

Smart Phone Addiction, Undergraduate Students, Nursing Students, Academic Performance,

Article History

Received: 25 December 2025

Accepted: 09 February 2026

Published: 24 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Roja Muskan

Abstract

Background: Smartphone addiction has become an increasing concern among undergraduate nursing students in recent years as a result of the widespread availability of digital innovation and the growing dependence on mobile devices for academic, clinical, and other purposes. Nursing students are particularly vulnerable because of their demanding academic schedules, clinical duties, and the need to stay constantly connected for educational and personal reasons.

Methodology: This study was a cross sectional, in which non-probability convenience sampling method was used and conducted from November 2025 to January 2026 at College of Nursing Female Nawabshah, sample size of this study was 109.

Results: The mean S.P.A score was 24.1 ± 2.4 . Second year found higher frequency of SPA. A majority subject missed planned work due to smartphone use 30(27.5%). In addition, a large number of study subject were hard time concentrating in class because of their smartphone 32(29.3%). Further most of study subject were felling impatient and uneasy without their smartphone 50 (45.8%). In addition, majority students felt pain in wrist and neck while they use smartphone 35 (32.1%).

Conclusion: The Current study conducted that prevalence of SPA (91.7%) among undergraduate nursing students in college of nursing Nawabshah.

Introduction: Smart phone (SP) is now a central part of modern life and have changed the way people communicate, study, and use their free time. (1) The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) conducted a study that found that Saudi Arabia had the highest percentage of mobile users worldwide. (2)The World Health Organization (WHO) defines addiction or dependence, as the continuous use of something for the sake of relief comfort, or stimulation, which often leads to excessive use, use despite harmful impact of

self or family, and occurrence of withdrawal symptoms including physical effects and craving when it is absent.(2,3) Smart phone addiction also has physical, psychological effects and behavior disorders. These includes disturbed sleep, headaches, eye strain, back and neck pain, stress, depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem.(4) More , problematic smart phone use correlates positively with insomnia and loneliness and negatively with self-esteem. (5,6) Smartphone are often misused while engaging in other activities like studying, walking, driving,

crossing the road, attending social events, and even before going to bed. (7) Depression is associated with a low mood, loss of interest or pleasure, guilt or low self-esteem, lack of appetite, low energy, poor concentration, and the possibility of suicidal ideation. (7,8) Additionally, Women have a greater propensity for social relationships, so they spent a significant amount of time using social networking, eventually leading them to become addicted to their smartphone. (9) Approximately 340 million people worldwide suffer from depression, which in turn contributes to a significant rate of suicidal ideation. (10) Smart phone is useful for quick approach to information, online classes, assignments and communication with teachers, peers and families. (11) At the same time, students also spend a large amount of time on social media, watching videos, and playing games. (12) Nursing students are particularly susceptible to the adverse effects of smartphone addiction due to the dual nature of their educational program, which combines theoretical coursework with intensive clinical training in healthcare settings. This unique blend of academic and practical demands places nursing students under considerable stress, making them more vulnerable to distractions such as excessive smartphone use. Existing literature globally has demonstrated a significant association between smartphone addiction and a range of negative outcomes, including elevated stress levels, poor sleep quality, depression, and diminished academic performance, particularly with respect to lower grades. However, within the context of Pakistan, there is a paucity of research focusing on the prevalence and impact of smartphone addiction among nursing students. This study aims to fill this gap by providing empirical evidence on the extent of smartphone addiction among nursing students at the College of Nawabshah, contributing to the broader understanding of how this issue affects the academic and psychological well-being of students in the healthcare education sector.

Material & Methods This study was cross sectional study, which is conducted from September to November 2025 at College of Nursing, Female Nawabshah. The non-probability convenient sampling technique was

used. The sample size was determined using the Rao-soft sample size calculator at a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 50% response distribution, and a target population of 150 nursing students. The required sample size was calculated as 109 undergraduate nursing students, at college of nursing, female Nawabshah.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Female BSN students.
2. Students who had been using smartphones for at least 1 year.
3. Students who were used smartphones for at least 2 hours daily.
4. GBSN student year, II, III, and IV.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Students who was not willing to participate.
2. Students who was not regular smartphone users.
3. GBSN student year I.

Tools for Data Collection: A structured questionnaire was used in this study, which is based on the (Smartphone Addiction Scale – Short Version: SAS-SV). The Smartphone Addiction Scale–Short Version is a widely used instrument to measure levels of smart phone addiction. It consists 10 questions to check how much a person depends on their smartphone. Each question is rated from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The total score ranges from 10 to 60, and a score of 33 or above shows smartphone addiction score among nursing students. The questionnaire was personally distributed to BSN students during their free time in class room. The purpose of the study was explained, and written consent was taken. Students were filled the questionnaires on the spot. Written informed consent was obtained from each student prior to participation. The students were instructed to complete the questionnaires on the spot to ensure completeness and accuracy of responses. The researcher also assured the participants that all information provided would remain strictly confidential and would be used for the purposes of this research study. Data was analyzed using basic descriptive statistics: Frequencies and percentages were calculated for demographic variables. To analyze the levels of smartphone addiction among BSN students, mean scores was

calculated using the Smartphone Addiction Scale – Short Version (SAS-SV). Furthermore,

Chi-Square test, and f-test applied, and ($p = \leq .05$) kept significant.

Result:

Table no.1: Demographic information:

Ser.	Item	Frequency (percentage)
1	Distribution of age of subject Minimum age Maximum age Mean S.D	21 33 24.1927 2.49621
2	Year of studying Second year Third year Fourth year	40 (36.7%) 35 (32.1%) 34 (31.2%)
3	Distribution of marital status Single Married	104 (95.4%) 5 (4.6%)
4	Average daily smartphone use Less than 2 hours 2-4 hours 5-7 hours	9 (8.3%) 32 (29.4%) 68 (62.4%)
5	Main purpose of smartphone use Social media use Study assignment Games, calls	41 (37.6%) 61 (56.0%) 7 (6.4%)

Table no.01 showed demographic data of the study participant. Age of subject was observed minimum age 21, maximum age 33, mean, 24.1 and S.D 2.4. In terms Year of study, second year students were more involved 40(36.7%) and third year, 35(32.1%) and fourth year 34(31.2%), regarding marital status majority of participate were single 104(95.4%), while married 5(4.6%). In addition, daily smartphone

use, the highest usage was reported for 5-7 hours among 68 (62.4%), 2-4 hours were recorded in 32 (29.4%) participants, while less than 2 hours was noted in 9 (8.3%). However, among participants main purpose of smartphone use was identified as study assignments in 61 (56.0%), Social media use was observed in 41 (37.6%) and games and calls were least reported, accounting for 7 (6.4%) participants.

Table no 2: Distribution of smartphone addition scale and age of subject.

SNO:	Item	Frequency (percentage %)	Pvalue
1.	I miss planned work due to smartphone use. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	9(8.2%) 31(28.4) 5(4.5%) 34(31.1%) 30(27.5%)	.003

2.	I have a hard time concentrating in class or work because of my smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	24(22.0%) 32(29.3%) 16(14.6%) 13(11.9%) 24(22.0%)	.041
3.	I feel impatient and uneasy without my smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	16(14.6%) 19(17.4%) 4(3.6%) 20(18.3%) 50(45.8%)	.001
4.	I have felt pain in the wrists or neck while using a smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	13(11.9%) 23(21.1%) 11(10.0%) 27(24.7%) 35(32.1%)	.002
5.	I will never give up using my smartphone even if it harms my daily life. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	29(26.6%) 32(29.3%) 14(12.8%) 9(8.2%) 25(22.9%)	.034
6.	I check my smartphone even when I am busy. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	9(8.2%) 32(29.3%) 8(7.3%) 18(16.5%) 42(38.5%)	.001
7.	I feel the need to use my smartphone again right after I stop using it. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6 (5.5%) 27 (24.7%) 12 (11.0%) 19 (17.4%) 45 (41.2%)	.041
8.	I use my smartphone longer than I had planned. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 5(4.5%) 26(23.8%) 48(44.0%)	.045

9.	I have tried to cut down smartphone use but failed. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 32(29.3%) 6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 41(37.6%)	.001
10.	People around me (family/friends) complain about my excessive smartphone use. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	29(26.6%) 40(36.6%) 6(5.5%) 8(7.3%) 26(23.8%)	.023

Table no.02 Most of study subject missed planned work due to smartphone use 30(27.5%) which have significant association ($p = .003$). In addition, majority of study subject were hard time concentrating in class because of their smartphone 32(29.3%) which showed significance associated with age ($p = .041$). Further most of study subject were felling impatient and uneasy without their smartphone 50 (45.8%), which showed significance associated with age ($p = .001$). Further most participant of study subject felt pain in wrist and neck while they use smartphone 35 (32.1%), which significance associated with age ($p = .002$). Further heavily attended of study subject were never stop using their smart phone even it harms 29(26.6%), significance with age ($p = .034$). In addition, most of study subject persistent

checked their smart phone while they were busy 42(38.5%), which significance associated with age ($p = .001$). Further most of study subject habitual behavior used smart phone 45(41.2%), which significant association with age ($p = .001$). In addition, multitude of study subject spending exceeding the time limits on their phone. 48(44.0%), which showed significance with age ($p = .041$). Further the large no, of study subject planed cut down the smartphone use but they unsuccessful 41(37.6%), which showed no significance with age ($p = .001$). In addition, bulk of people of study subject complained from family and friends on excessive use of their smartphone 40(36.6%), and have significant association with the age, and smart phone adduction ($p = .023$).

Table no 3: Distribution of smartphone addition scale and year of study of subject.

SNO:	Item	Frequency (percentage %)	Pvalue
1.	I miss planned work due to smartphone use. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	9(8.2%) 31(28.4) 5(4.5%) 34(31.1%) 30(27.5%)	.048
2.	I have a hard time concentrating in class or work because of my smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	24(22.0%) 32(29.3%) 16(14.6%) 13(11.9%) 24(22.0%)	.043

3.	I feel impatient and uneasy without my smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	16(14.6%) 19(17.4%) 4(3.6%) 20(18.3%) 50(45.8%)	.046
4.	I have felt pain in the wrists or neck while using a smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	13(11.9%) 23(21.1%) 11(10.0%) 27(24.7%) 35(32.1%)	.031
5.	I will never give up using my smartphone even if it harms my daily life. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	29(26.6%) 32(29.3%) 14(12.8%) 9(8.2%) 25(22.9%)	.002
6.	I check my smartphone even when I am busy. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	9(8.2%) 32(29.3%) 8(7.3%) 18(16.5%) 42(38.5%)	.014
7.	I feel the need to use my smartphone again right after I stop using it. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 27(24.7%) 12(11.0%) 19(17.4%) 45(41.2%)	.001
8.	I use my smartphone longer than I had planned. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 5(4.5%) 26(23.8%) 48(44.0%)	.031
9.	I have tried to cut down smartphone use but failed. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 32(29.3%) 6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 41(37.6%)	.003

10.	People around me (family/friends) complain about my excessive smartphone use.		.013
	Strongly disagree	29(26.6%)	
	Disagree	40(36.6%)	
	Neutral	6(5.5%)	
	Agree	8(7.3%)	
	Strongly Agree	26(23.8%)	

Table no.03 Most of study subject missed planned work due to smartphone use 30(27.5%) which have significant association ($p = .048$). In addition, majority of study subject were hard time concentrating in class because of their smartphone 32(29.3%) and have significant association ($p = .043$). Further most of study subject were feeling impatient and uneasy without their smartphone 50 (45.8%), and have significant association ($p = .046$). Most participant of study subject felt pain in wrist and neck while they use smartphone 35 (32.1%), also have significant association ($p = .031$). Moreover, heavily attended of study subject were never stop using their smart phone even it harms 29(26.6%), which significance association ($p = .002$). In addition, most of study subject

persistent checked their smart phone while they were busy 42(38.5%), and ($p = .014$). A large group have habitual behavior used smart phone 45(41.2%), which have significance association ($p = .001$). In addition, multitude of study subject spending exceeding the time limits on their phone. 48(44.0%), which showed no significance with year of study ($p = .031$). Furthermore the large number of study subject planed cut down the smartphone use but they unsuccessful 41(37.6%), and have strongly association ($p = .003$). In addition, bulk of people of study subject, they had complained from family and friends on excessive use of their smartphone 40(36.6%), and also have significant association ($p = .013$).

Table no 4: Distribution of smartphone addition scale main purpose of smartphone use of subject.

SNO:	Item	Frequency (percentage %)	Pvalue
1.	I miss planned work due to smartphone use.		.031
	Strongly disagree	9(8.2%)	
	Disagree	31(28.4)	
	Neutral	5(4.5%)	
	Agree	34(31.1%)	
	Strongly Agree	30(27.5%)	
2.	I have a hard time concentrating in class or work because of my smartphone.		.012
	Strongly disagree	24(22.0%)	
	Disagree	32(29.3%)	
	Neutral	16(14.6%)	
	Agree	13(11.9%)	
	Strongly Agree	24(22.0%)	
3.	I feel impatient and uneasy without my smartphone.		.05
	Strongly disagree		
	Disagree	16(14.6%)	
	Neutral	19(17.4%)	
	Agree	4(3.6%)	
	Strongly Agree	20(18.3%)	
		50(45.8%)	

4.	I have felt pain in the wrists or neck while using a smartphone. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	13(11.9%) 23(21.1%) 11(10.0%) 27(24.7%) 35(32.1%)	.001
5.	I will never give up using my smartphone even if it harms my daily life. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	29(26.6%) 32(29.3%) 14(12.8%) 9(8.2%) 25(22.9%)	.003
6.	I check my smartphone even when I am busy. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	9(8.2%) 32(29.3%) 8(7.3%) 18(16.5%) 42(38.5%)	.014
7.	I feel the need to use my smartphone again right after I stop using it. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 27(24.7%) 12(11.0%) 19(17.4%) 45(41.2%)	.001
8.	I use my smartphone longer than I had planned. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 5(4.5%) 26(23.8%) 48(44.0%)	.014
9.	I have tried to cut down smartphone use but failed. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	6(5.5%) 32(29.3%) 6(5.5%) 24(22.0%) 41(37.6%)	.003
10.	People around me (family/friends) complain about my excessive smartphone use. Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree	29(26.6%) 40(36.6%) 6(5.5%) 8(7.3%) 26(23.8%)	.034

Table no.04: Most of study subject missed planned work due to smartphone use 30(27.5%), and strongly associated ($p = .031$). In addition, most of study subject were hard time

concentrating in class because of their smartphone 32(29.3%) which showed significance associated with main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .012$). Further most of study

subject were felling impatient and uneasy without their smartphone 50 (45.8%), which showed no significance associated with main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .05$). Further most participant of study subject felt pain in wrist and neck while they use smartphone 35 (32.1%), statically significance associated with main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .001$). Further heavily attended of study subject were never stop using their smart phone even it harms 29(26.6%), significance with main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .003$). In addition, most of study subject persistent checked their smart phone while they were busy 42(38.5%), which have significance with main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .014$). Further most of study subject habitual behavior used smart phone 45(41.2%), which, and strongly associated with smartphone use ($p = .001$). In addition, multitude of study subject spending exceeding the time limits on their phone. 48(44.0%), and main purpose of smartphone use ($p = .003$). In addition, bulk of people of study subject, complained from family and friends on excessive use of their smartphone 40(36.6%), and strongly association with smartphone use ($p = .034$).

Discussion:

This is a descriptive cross-sectional study, in which non probability convenience sampling technique was used, the aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of smart phone addiction at college of nursing female Nawabshah. The current study reported the prevalence of smart phone addiction at College of Nursing, Nawabshah was (91.7%), which a alarming situation among nurses. Furthermore, use of smart phone the current study reported that the mean age of participants was (21-33, $SD \pm 2.49$) these findings compared with geetika singh et al 2025, in India conducted mean age of (20-64, $SD \pm 1.98$). (14,15). The current study reported that the (36.7%) of second year students, (32.1%) of third year student and (31.2%) of fourth year students are agreed that they are addicted the smartphone, these findings compared with geetika singh et al 2025, (30.6%) of second year students, (25.2%) of third year students and (31.2%) of fourth year students are agreed that they are addicted the smartphone. (16,17) The current study reports (95.4%)

participants were single, while (4.6%) were married, this finding compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, most of the subjects were single (98.8%) while only (9.2%) was married. (18,19,20) Further, the current study reported that (8.3%) were the students use less than 2 hours per day on their phone, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, (54.1%) of student use the screen time more than half hour per day. (19,20) The current study reported (29.4%) of participants spent 2-4 hours per day on smartphone, this finding compared with panida haniphitakphong PT et al 2021, (48.8%) of the participants spent 1-4 hours per day on their smartphone. (21,22) The current study reported (62.4%) participants use their smartphone 5-7 hours per day, this finding compared with zahid M et al 2021, almost (48%) of the users are found to use smartphone and other gadgets for about 5-7 hours per day. (23,24) The current study reported the (37.6%) participants used social media, these findings compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, large number of participants (88.8%) used smartphone for social media, In addition current study reported the (56.0%) of participants used smartphone for assignments purpose while (6.4%) participants used for call and entertainments, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, most of subject (76.5%) used smartphone for assignments purpose and (49%) utilized smartphone for entertainment and calls. (24,25,26) The current study reported that (31.1%) were students missed planned work due to smartphone, this finding compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, students (51.6%) were agreed that they missed planned work because of smartphone.(26) The current study reported that (22.0%) participants hard to concentrating in work due to smartphone use, compared with geetika singh et al 2025, (38.2%) difficulty concentrating due to phone use.(27) The current study reported (45.8%) of participants were felt impatient without smartphone, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, most of subjects (36%) were feeling impatient when they not holding their smartphone. (22,23,28) The current study reported (32.1%) were felt pain in the wrist or neck while using smartphone, this finding compared with geetika singh et al 2025, (43%) were participants feel pain in wrist or neck from smartphone use.(22,23,25) The current

study reported around (29.3%) of participant were never give up using their smartphone even it effected on daily life, compared with geetika singh et al 2025, about (40%) of students believed that they will never give up using smartphone even when their daily life affected (17,22,23). The current study reported (38.5%) were habitual with checked their smartphone even when they busy, compared with geetika singh et al 2025, (67.2%) were participant checked their smartphone habitually. The current study reported that (41.2%) were checked their smartphone again right after they stop using, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, (67.2%) were participant agreed to constantly checking their smartphone. (17,22,23).

The current study reported that (44.0%) of participant used smartphone longer then they planned, this finding compared with geetika singh et al 2025, (80.5%) were students use phone longer then intended.(23,24)The current study reported that the most of participant (37.6%) were tried to cut down the use of smartphone but they failed, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, around (36%) of participant agreed to will not be able to stand not having a smartphone.(21,29) The current study reported that (36.6%) were participant told us the people around they complained on too much smartphone uses, compared with sunita A AZ Ali et al 2024, (60.5%) agreed that the people around us tell me that they use of smart phone too much.(29,30,31)

Conclusion:

The current study reveals a significant prevalence of smartphone addiction (91.7%).. Furthermore, smartphone addiction (SPA) has been found to disrupt the daily routines of nursing students, leading to decreased engagement in academic pursuits and a notable reduction in participation during class activities. These findings underscore the negative impact of smartphone addiction on both the academic performance and overall well-being of nursing students at the College of Nursing Nawabshah.

Recommendation: This was a cross-sectional study, conducted only in a college of nursing (Female) , limited time, and female students were enrolled , so there is need to conduct the

longitudinal study to determine cause and its effect.

Funding: Self.

Conflict of Interest: No any.

REFERENCES:

1. Çelik B, Atas AH. A Correlational Study on Mobile Phone Addiction among University Students: Prevalence, Student Characteristics, Mobile Phone Use Purposes, and Situations. *Eur J Psychol Educ Res.* 2023;volume-6-2(volume-6-issue-3-september-2023):131-45.
2. Kalal N, Vel NS, Angmo S, Choyal S, Bishnoi S, Dhaka S, et al. Smartphone addiction and its impact on quality of sleep and academic performance among nursing students. Institutional based cross-sectional study in Western Rajasthan (India). *Investig y Educ en Enferm.* 2023;41(2).
3. Abid U, Khan TJ, Sheikh A, Saleem S, Kayani HA, Habib MA. The relationship between smartphone addiction and depression among university students in Karachi: a cross-sectional study. *Int J Community Med Public Heal.* 2020;7(9):3472.
4. Yadav R, Arora S, ... UP... NJ of, 2025 undefined. Smartphone Addiction, Insomnia, Loneliness, and Self-Esteem Among Nursing Students: A Correlation Study. *pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov* Yadav, S Arora, U Phalswal, P Dixit Florence Nightingale J Nursing, 2025 • *pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*.
5. Kalaitzaki A, Laconi S, Spritzer DT, Hauck S, Gnisci A, Sergi I, et al. The Prevalence and Predictors of Problematic Mobile Phone Use: a 14-Country Empirical Survey. *Int J Ment Health Addict.* 2024;22(1):746-65.
6. Sayeed MA, Rasel MSR, Habibullah AA, Hossain MM. Prevalence and underlying factors of mobile game addiction among university students in Bangladesh. *Glob Ment Heal.* 2021;8.

7. Özdil K, Çatiker A, Bulucu Büyüksoy GD. Smartphone addiction and perceived pain among nursing students: a cross-sectional study. 2022;27(10):2246-60.
8. Machado J, Pai R, Health RKJ of E and, 2023 undefined. The pattern of smartphone usage, smartphone addiction, and associated subjective health problems associated with smartphone use among undergraduate nursing. journals.lww.comJ Machado, RR Pai, RR KotianJournal Educ Heal Promot 2023 •journals.lww.com.
9. Sadeghi N, Rezaeian S, Janatolmakan M, Heidarian P, Khatony A. Exploring the prevalence of nomophobia, its contributing factors, and the relationship with social interaction anxiety among nursing students. SpringerN Sade S Rezaeian, M Janatolmakan, P Heidarian, A KhatonyBMC Med Educ 2025 •Springer. 2025 Dec;25(1).
10. Sarmad S, Zaman I, Bibi A, ... NA... (Journal of N&, 2025 undefined. Correlation of Smart Phone Addiction and Academic Performance among Nursing Students of Private Nursing Colleges in Swat: Correlation of Smart Phone Addiction. nursearcher.comSMA Sarmad, I Zaman, A Bibi, N Ali, S Ahmad, SW Akbar, M KamalNURSEARCHER (Journal Nurs Midwifery Sci 2025 •nursearcher.com. 2025;
11. Bilgic S, Aktas A, ... MAIJ of, 2023 undefined. Smartphone Addiction and Peer Relations in Nursing Students. search.ebscohost.com.
12. Meng SQ, Cheng JL, Li YY, Yang XQ, Zheng JW, Chang XW, et al. Global prevalence of digital addiction in general population: A systematic review and meta-analysis. Clin Psychol Rev. 2022;92(December 2021).
13. Jain P. The Impact of Smartphone Addiction on Social Skills and Play Behaviour Among. 2025;1-7.
14. Bitlis F, Üniversitesi E. the Pandemic Period: The Case of Bitlis Eren University Öz Anahtar Kelimeler Keywords. 2022;2022:79-96.
15. Ogunmodede JA, Ogunmodede AJ, Ahmed A, Buhari OIN, Agede OA, Bojuwoye MO, et al. PREVALENCE AND PREDICTORS OF PROBLEMATIC. 2023;10(1):1-18.
16. Feizollahi Z, Asadzadeh H, Mousavi SR, Asadzadeh H. Research Paper Prediction of Symptoms of Psychosomatic Disorders in University Students Based on Perfectionism Mediated by Smartphone Addiction. 2022;7(3):151-8.
17. Hanphitakphong P, Keeratisiroj O, Thawinchai N. Smartphone addiction and its association with upper body musculoskeletal symptoms among university students classified by age and gender. J Phys Ther Sci. 2021;33(5):394-400.
18. Wahid E, Khalil S, Ali A, Khan MS, Intikhab M, Ali M, et al. The Healer Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation Sciences. 2025;5(2):125-31.
19. Zahid M. Prevalence of Smartphone Addiction Among Students of Colleges of Rehabilitation Sciences. Pakistan J Rehabil. 2021;10(2):14-8.
20. Wahyuni S. Nomophobia (No MOBILE PHone PhoBIA) among Medical students: A literature review. 2022;2(3):48-51.
21. Saritepeci M, Durak HY, Uslu NA. A Latent Profile Analysis for the Study of Multiple Screen Addiction , Mobile Social Gaming Addiction , General Mattering , and Family Sense of Belonging in University. Int J Ment Health Addict [Internet]. 2022;(0123456789). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-022-00816-y>
22. Zeerak Q, Imran M, Azeez K, Lokanathan TH, Ismail IM. The Effects of Smartphone Addiction on Academic Performance Among Undergraduate Medical Students in Karnataka , India : A Multi-centric Study. 2024;16(6).

23. Abuhamdah SMA. Smart phone addiction and its mental health risks among university students in Jordan : a cross-sectional study. 2023;1-9.
24. Gangadharan N, Borle AL, Basu S. Mobile Phone Addiction as an Emerging Behavioral Form of Addiction Among Adolescents in India. 2022;14(4):7-15.
25. Azam M, Ali A, Mattiullah J, Perveen N. PHYSICAL ACTIVITY , SPORTS PARTICIPATION , AND SMARTPHONE ADDICTION IN ADOLESCENT STUDENTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW. 2020;20(1):25-41.
26. Desouky DE sayed, Abu-zaid H. Mobile phone use pattern and addiction in relation to depression and anxiety. 2020;26(6).
27. Salim ID, Abdul N, Jamal R. Prevalence of Mobile Phone Addiction among Students in Institute Technical of Kut Students ` gender. 2017;1(5):400-5.
28. Singh G, Singh S. Prevalence of Smartphone Addiction and Its Association With Sleep Quality Among Medical Undergraduates : A Cross-Sectional Study From Eastern India Sociodemographic profile. 2025;17(10).
29. Gizem F, Yilmaz K, Avci U, Yilmaz R. The role of loneliness and aggression on smartphone addiction among university students. *Curr Psychol [Internet]*. 2022;(0123456789). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03018-w>
30. Kalaitzaki A, Laconi S, Tornaim D. The Prevalence and Predictors of Problematic Mobile Phone Use : a 14 - Country Empirical Survey. *Int J Ment Health Addict [Internet]*. 2022;(0123456789). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11469-022-00901-2>
31. Rasheed R, Navied U, Mirza H, Ali H, Mansoor A, Ziasahi B. Problematic mobile phone use and sleep quality in medical students : A cross-sectional study. 2025;6(2):83.